

Phenological Study of Some Forest Trees of Pali, Rajasthan

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Abstract

The present study shows the phenological events such as leaf fall, flushing, flowering and fruiting of some tree species of Pali region which is located in south western side of Rajasthan. The region is dominated by some tree species such as *Anogessus latifolia*, *Acacia leucophloea*, *Boswellia serrata* and *Bombex ceiba*. Phenological events are closely related to ecoclimatic factors like temperature, moisture and humidity of the region. Phenological observation of different tree species were recorded periodically throughout the study. Single peak for each event occurring one after another was observed for most of the tree species. Phenological observation during present investigation showed leaf fall in January- February, leaf fall and flowers in March-April followed by fruiting in April-June.

Keywords

Phenology, Deciduous, Leaf fall, Flowering, Fruiting.

Introduction

Phenology is the study of timing of seasonal biological activities of plants. The term was first introduced in 1853 by the Belgian botanist Charles Morren and is derived from Greek words *phaino* meaning "to appear, to come into view" and *logos*, meaning "to study" (Brian P.Haggerty and Susan J Mazer 2008). Phenological changes can be monitored and their effects on health, biodiversity, nutrient cycling, forestry, agriculture, and the economy have marked. (Schwartz 2013). Phenology is the study of the time of recurring natural phenomena in plants which deals with new foliage, leaf fall, flowering, and fruiting like events (Nakar and Jadeja, 2014). Pattern of phenological events is variously used for characterization of vegetation type (Shimwell1972; Opler et al.1980). In forest land displacement and adjustment of flowering and fruiting of different species is very important for pollinators and seed dispersal agents (Janzen,1970; Arroyo,1979). Phenological events show a keen relationship with climatic factors and periodic phenomenon in different seasons.Drought is one of most common environmental stress that affects growth and development of plants (Aslam et.al.2006). Therefore, these phenological events (leafing, flowering, fruiting etc.) are sensitive to climate change. Phenology of tree in any ecosystem and community strongly determines the flowering periods which is indirectly dependent on the environmental variations. (Zhang et al. 2006).

India has wide range of vegetation type. Precise phenological information with respect to flowering and fruiting evaluated against leafing and leafless period is scarce in tropical deciduous forest in India which account for about 46% of the forested land in the country (Singh and Singh).

Aim of study

Phenological study has not been carried out properly from the study area, hence the record provided here may be utilized for further climate change assessment.

Review of Literature

Numata et al. (2003) showed that the flower production of tropical canopy trees was triggered by prolonged drought, high, solar radiation, and abnormally low temperature. Kikuzawa and Lechowicz (2010) concluded that phenological studies are also important

to understand ecosystem processes such as plant growth pattern, biomass production, plant water stress. Fu et al. (2015) have been founded the effects of global warming on plant phenological traits. Boesch (2013) studied the long-term changes in fruit phenology of West African tropical rain forest and observed decrease in rainfall have a negative impact on fruit phenology. Nakar and Jadeja (2014) studied the phenology of two Bombacaceae members from Girnar reserve forest, Gujrat. Tripathi (2018) studied the phenology of some dominant tree species of Ajmer region of Rajasthan. Negi et. al. (2021) studied the effect of atmospheric warming on phenological earliness and length of growing season in Himalayan trees. Mittal et. al. (2021) studied the patterns of phenological characteristics of tree species of Kumaun Himalayan region. Singh et. al. (2023) observed phenological variations with respect to climatic variables of moist temperate forest tree species of Western Himalaya.

Methodology

Site of study and Methodology-

Pali is located between 24 °45' to 26°45' north latitude and 72°48' to 74°2' east longitudes. The area of the district may be called sub mountainous and has undulated plains with scattered hills. This district is surrounded by Aravali range on its south east. The climate of the district is dry and has extremes of temperature. It is hot during summer and very cold during winter. The winter season is from November to March and is followed by the summer from April to June. The period from July to mid-September forms the south west monsoon season and mid-September to October is the post monsoon season. January is the coldest month list. The mean daily maximum temperature is 34.1°C and minimum is 19.0°C. The average maximum rainfall is 153.7 mm and average maximum relative humidity is 85.5% maximum rainfall is recorded in the month of August and maximum relative humidity is record in the month of September. For detailed phenological observation a list of forest tree species of Pali was prepared.